

RAISING A CHILD IN A DYSFUNCTIONAL FAMILY

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Abstract. In real life, a dysfunctional family is no laughing matter. Families caught in the cycle of dysfunction often face serious abusive issues like alcohol abuse, drug abuse, domestic violence, physical abuse, sexual abuse, and emotional abuse. This type of environment can be toxic to children, and unfortunately, family problems never end there. Children of dysfunctional families tend to carry on the cycle of dysfunction into their own lives and into their own families.

Key words: distressed or abusive environments, substance abuse, mental illness, chronic physical illness, and poor communication.

The main part.

Parenting may appear to be a personal matter. It is a parent's right to decide how to raise their child. Nonetheless, researchers consider it the most important public health issue facing our society. Poor parenting has a serious impact on not only the child but also on society as a whole. Physically, poor parenting, such as child abuse, including physical abuse, emotional abuse, or emotional neglect, can harm a child or put them or others in dangerous situations.

Psychologically, bad parenting skills lead to children's development and mental health problems. Dysfunctional parenting can cause two major types of mental health issues: internalizing problems such as depression, anxiety, or personality disorders, and externalizing problems, such as aggression and violence.

Studies show that poor parenting, especially aggressive punishment, is one of the biggest causes of externalizing behavior that leads to juvenile delinquency.

Bad childhood may lead to crimes, drug addiction, or alcoholism in adulthood. It can also lead to teenage pregnancy, substance abuse, truancy, school disruption, and a cycle of abuse with their own children. Most people define bad parenting in one of two ways: by the behavior of parents or by the outcome/behavior of children.

There are many problems with these two types of definitions. First, a parent can be unfairly judged by their behavior alone, because parenting behaviors do not always reflect their intent. Most of us did not learn how to be a good parent in school. As new parents, we often do what we know, whether from our own experience or from watching or listening to others. We do not know what we do not know. Even with the best of intentions, parents can make mistakes. Being uninformed and making mistakes doesn't necessarily mean they are bad parents. Second, a child's behavior or success/failure alone can not represent parenting quality because there are many factors that can influence a child. Children can thrive despite awful parenting, while others can falter or show bad behavior even with good parenting.

It is not uncommon for lousy parents to take credit for good results when their kids succeed despite terrible parenting. They justify their poor parenting with how well their kids do behaviorally, financially, or professionally. They often ignore the psychological scars they have left on their children. This is an injustice for those kids. The children, not the parents, should get the credit for surviving bad parenting actions.

Conversely, some children do not do well in life, even if they have good parents, because other factors can have adverse effects on development, too. Parents have no control over everything in their children's lives even if they try.

Conclusion.

A family is the single most important influence in a child's life. It provides security, identity, and values to its members, regardless of their age. An individual learns about his sense of self and gains a foundation for the rest of his life. This foundation includes the family's values which provide the basis for his own moral code. Therefore, the parenting style that parents adopt while raising children can have a huge impact on their development and growth.

Now, imagine the mental condition of a child, especially a toddler, brought up in an environment where problems such as parental negligence, rigidity, alcoholism or abuse exist in the family, disturbing its smooth functioning, leading to constant conflicts, fights, arguments, and tension. Through this blog post, we share what a dysfunctional family is, the types, signs, effects of such family on children, and how to overcome these problems.

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